

Role of PMFBY in Agricultural Development in Marathwada Region

Dr. N. B. Kale¹ **Asst. Prof. N. B. Nagare**²

¹HOD, Dept. of Commerce, Tuljabhani Mahavidyalaya, Tuljapur

²HOD, Dept. of Commerce, R. P. College, Osmanabad

Email: kalenetaji123@gmail.com

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Abstract

Marathwada is a one of the region of Maharashtra state. It is known as a drought prone area. More than 50 per cent population are affected due to short rainfall and other Natural hazard. At the same time, more than 70% of total population was depended on agriculture. So the government of India introduced PMFBY in Feb. 2016 for agriculture development. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) is the one of the largest crop insurance scheme, which is helps to agriculture development. In this study, main focused on performance of PMFBY and agriculture development in marathwada region in Maharashtra state. For detailed study, we collected the secondary data about PMFBY and analyzed on the four indicates I.e. Farmer's participation, Area covered, Premium and Government Subsidy and Sum Insured.

Keywords: Insurance, Marathwada Region, Maharashtra, Agriculture development, Government subsidy, Role of PMFBY

Introduction:

Marathwada is a one of the region of Maharashtra state. It is known as a drought prone area. More than 50 per cent population are affected due to short rainfall and other Natural hazard. At the same time, more than 70% of total population was depended on agriculture. The agriculture secures faces the lot of challenges due to uncertainties in agriculture i.e. natural and artificial hazards especially Marathwada region in Maharashtra state. Still, more people in Marathwada region make money for their livelihood from this sector, than from all other economic sectors.

Marathwada region has totally depended on agriculture and the agriculture sectors continue affected due to Natural hazard. The Government of India has developed various strategies to reduce agricultural risk and uncertainty. Mainly in it include providing tax remission, waiving off loans and interest, drought or flood relief measures, etc. Even so, a major problem with such types of relief is that such measures be dependent primarily on government policy as well as resources. However, these measures provide some guarantee and security in case of uncertainty, it is possible to expect some relief as the government is on their side when farmers are at a loss.

Although all the above matters are being done at the government level, the

problems of the farmers are increasing day by day. In the first six months of 2020 in Maharashtra, 310 farmers have committed suicide in Marathwada. This number is lower than in the last six years. In the first six months, 413 farmers committed suicide. Drought-hit Marathwada farmer suicide is a serious problem, Aurangabad Division, Jalna, Parbhani, Beed, Osmanabad, Nanded, Latur and Hingoli are the eight Marathwada districts under Aurangabad Division. Beed district has the highest number of suicides this year, followed by Osmanabad with 56, Jalna and Nanded with 53. There have been 20 suicides in Hingoli.

Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) is the one of the largest crop insurance scheme, which is helps to agriculture development. PMFBY was introduced in Feb. 2016. In this study, main focused on performance of PMFBY and agriculture development in marathwada region in Maharashtra state.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of concern study are as follows.

1. To study about role of crop insurance schemes in Agriculture development
2. To measure the performance of crop insurance scheme for agriculture development

3. To analyze the farmers' participation, area insured and gross premium of crop insurance scheme

Research methodology

Data Collection: This is an analytical study; hence, Secondary data is an important and powerful tool for the any type of research. Researcher conducted his research work is on the basis of secondary data. The secondary data is collected through newspapers, magazine, government reports and internet. For accomplishing the objectives of the study, three years data is collected and analyzed it.

Research area: The present study deals with the role of PMFBY and agriculture development. For justify the subject & detailed study proposes, PMFBY are selected in Marathwada region.

Limitations of the study: In this study, only PMFBY was selected and only five years performance was measured of the agriculture insurance scheme in Marathwada region in Maharashtra stae. Other crop insurance schemes are not taken into account.

Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)

Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) is one of the world's largest and important crop insurance scheme. It's aimed to providing risk cover to Indian farmers. PMFBY was launched in early 2016 with the key feature being a highly subsidized and affordable premium to farmers. Under the scheme, only 2% premium of maximum to pay farmers during Kharif sowing, 1.5% during Rabi sowing for food and oilseed crops, whereas for annual commercial crops they have to pay a maximum of 5%. As a same, the Government of India and state government shared equally pay the subsidy on farmer's premium of actuarial premium rate. The National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS) as well as the modified NAIS has combined into PMFBY.

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The role of crop insurance scheme especially PMFBY measured with the help of some indicators. It includes farmer's participation, Area insured, Premium paid

and Sum insured by farmers as well as government subsidy. The performance are evaluated in Kharif season 2018-2020 and

Rabi Season 2018-2021 of Marathwada region in Maharashtra state.

Farmer's participation:

During last three years, in Kharif 2018-2020 and Rabi 2018-2021, total of 1.11 crore farmers participated under PMFBY in Marathwada Region. The more farmers were participated in Kharif season as a compare to Rabi season. In kharif-2018, total 31.56 lac, Kharif-2019, total 28.15 lac and Kharif-2020, total 25.33 farmers were participated during last three years. It shows the participation of farmers are decreased in Marathwada region.

As per the PMFBY report 2018 to 2020, the Latur district took first place in farmers participation with 22.58 lac farmers. Also, Bid and Nanded district took second and third place in participation respectively.

As per agriculture census, there had a total number of 3480702 frames, which is averagely 1851785 farmers participated in Marathwada region in Kharif and rabi season under PMFBY. It shows that 52.20 per cent farmers had participated in PMFBY during last three years and it is helpful to agriculture development.

Area covered:

The total area insured in kharif and Rabi taken together has 14451.66 thousand hectors from 2018 to 2021. The area under PMFBY has decreased year to year. As a compared to Rabi season, in Kharif season 2018 to 2021, the area covered under PMFBY has more. Following chart 02 indicates the performance in Area Covered in PMFBY in Marathwada region from 2018-19 to 2020-21.

As per PMFBY report, it shows that Bid, Latur and Osmanabad took first, second and third place in area covered under PMFBY in Marathwada region during 2018-19 to 2020-21. As per agriculture census, total agriculture area has 52361.7 thousand hectors and only 14451.66 thousand hectors area under PMFBY in Marathwada region. It indicates that only 27.60 per cent area were covered under PMFBY in Marathwada region.

Premium and Government Subsidy:

The premium paid by the farmers from 2018 to 2021 had 110575.98 lac and state and central government had paid 1099843.71 lac in that period. The gross premium has increased from year to year. During 2018 to 2021, the state and central government commonly paid subsidy under PMFBY has 90.86 per cent. The government of India plays most important role through provide subsidy for insuring crops.

Sum Insured:

The total sum insured in Marathwada region has increased regularly during 2018-19 to 2020-21. the total value of sum insured under PMFBY has Rs.5,073,874.10 lac from last three years in Marathwada region and Rs. 12,751,100.28 lac in Maharashtra state. Bed, Latur and Osmanabad stood a first, second and third rank in sum insured. As a compare to Maharashtra, 40 per cent value of sum insured in Marathwada region. So it is clearly indicates that, the government always tray to develop agriculture sectors.

Conclusion:

As per the performance evaluate of PMFBY during 2018 to 2021 in Marathwada region, the number of farmers participation, area covered under PMFBY and sum insured had declined from last four year but in 2021-2022 was increased. Apart from Premium and government subsidy had increased. There is need to motivate the farmers towards crop insurance scheme. It is possible when the ground level motivation camp will be organized door to door in every village. On the basis of conclusion, there is need too much more efforts in PMFBY to sustainable development in agriculture.

Bibliography

1. Ashok Gulati, (Feb. 2018), Crop Insurance in India: Key Issues and Way Forward, Working paper NO. 352
2. Singh, G. (2010), "Crop Insurance in India", IIM Ahmedabad, Working Paper. No. 2010-06- 01
3. Ministry of Agriculture & farmers welfare Govt. of India; PMFBY Progress and achievement 2016 to 2021 report
4. <https://pmfby.gov.in/adminStatistics/dashboard>

5. https://pmfby.gov.in/pdf/New%20Scheme-s-english_.pdf
6. https://pmfby.gov.in/ext/rpt/ssfr_17
7. Hazell, P., Pomareda, C., and Valdes, A. (1986), "Crop Insurance for Agricultural Development", John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, USA Harms, S.C, "History of Crop Insurance in the United States", Retrieved from